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Impact Of Parental Involvement In School Management On Pupils' Academic Performance In Public Primary Schools In Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of parental involvement in school management on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study, while two hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 5,561 teachers from 795 public primary schools in Benue North-East Senatorial District. Using a multistage sampling procedure, a sample of 371 teachers was selected from 37 public primary schools. The Parental Involvement and Pupils' Academic Performance Questionnaire (PIPAPQ) was validated by three experts and a trial test was conducted, which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.97. mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions, while chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness-of-fit was used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that parents' involvement in school financing and maintenance of school infrastructure have significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others, that government and education policymakers should develop and strengthen policies that encourage active parental participation in school financing through structured mechanisms such as Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) and community-based funding initiatives. School administrators should ensure transparency and accountability in the utilization of such funds to encourage parents to contribute regularly and responsibly to support school needs.

Keywords: parental involvement, school financing, maintenance of school infrastructure, school management and pupils' academic performance

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance in education reflects the overall effectiveness of the teaching–learning process and the degree to which educational objectives are successfully attained. It embodies the quality of knowledge, skills, values, and competencies learners acquire, which shape their preparedness for higher education, the world of work, and responsible citizenship. However, global evidence suggests a noticeable decline in pupils' academic performance, posing a significant challenge to educational systems worldwide. This decline has been linked to factors such as socio-economic inequality, disruptions arising from the COVID-19 pandemic, economic recession, shortages of qualified teachers, and low levels of

parental involvement, all of which have widened learning gaps, particularly in foundational areas like literacy and numeracy (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2021).

This downward trend not only affects pupils' current learning outcomes but also threatens long-term economic and social development, as future workforces may lack the essential skills required in an increasingly knowledge-based global economy (UNESCO, 2021). For instance, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) found that, in many countries worldwide, pupils scored lower on assessments in post-pandemic than in previous years, particularly in literacy and numeracy, which are foundational skills (OECD, 2022). Similarly, UNESCO (2020) reports that in low- and middle-income countries, only about 10% of children reach minimum reading proficiency by age ten, highlighting widespread learning deficits. This issue seems particularly pronounced in Nigeria and many other African countries, which seem to have been grappling with persistently low learner performance for some time, yet have not implemented effective, lasting solutions.

Pupils' academic performance is commonly defined as the level of knowledge and skill a learner demonstrates in various subject areas, often measured through standardized tests, assessments and teacher evaluations (OECD, 2020). Furthermore, academic performance has been described as the degree to which learners attain prescribed instructional goals, commonly determined through measurable outcomes such as examination scores, continuous assessment results, and teachers' ratings across core subjects including mathematics, reading, and science (Brookhart, 2018). It signifies the learner's capacity to comprehend, internalize, and effectively utilize acquired knowledge and skills, thereby functioning as a key indicator of academic achievement and educational progress (OECD, 2020).

Academic performance encompasses both core academic subjects, such as literacy, numeracy, and science, and broader competencies, including critical thinking and problem-solving, that are essential for personal and professional growth (World Bank, 2021). High academic performance indicates that learners meet or exceed set educational standards, reflecting not only their learning achievements but also the quality of educational support they receive. In contrast, low performance often highlights gaps in learning, which can limit future opportunities and underscore underlying issues within the educational system (UNICEF, 2022). Understanding and improving academic performance, therefore, remain central goals for teachers and policymakers worldwide, as they seek to equip learners with the skills needed in an evolving global economy.

Assessing pupils' academic performance requires multiple approaches, combining quantitative scores with qualitative insights to build a comprehensive view of learners' progress. Standardized tests provide a widely used benchmark for comparing performance across regions and for identifying areas of improvement, while other methods, such as classroom assignments and project-based evaluations, offer a more detailed view of learners' ability to apply knowledge in diverse contexts (UNESCO, 2022). Research today underscores the importance of examining academic performance through this multifaceted lens to understand better pupils' readiness for real-world challenges and lifelong learning (OECD, 2021). Beyond individual efforts, academic outcomes are influenced by a range of factors, including socio-economic background, the quality of school resources, teacher expertise, and, especially, parental involvement in education (World Bank, 2022). Darling-Hammond (2020) and Fan and Chen (2021) highlighted several variables influencing pupils' academic performance, including socio-economic factors, teacher quality, and parental involvement. Pupils from low socio-economic backgrounds may face barriers, such as limited access to learning resources, which can hinder their academic success (Bradley & Corwyn, 2022). The quality of teachers and active parental involvement in school activities play a vital role in improving learners' academic outcomes. In contrast, factors such as poor school infrastructure and low student motivation can hinder academic achievement. This study, however, focuses on the impact of parental involvement in school management, specifically in school financing, infrastructure maintenance, decision-making, discipline, and homework monitoring and support. The research will explore how these factors influence pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in the Benue North East Senatorial District of Nigeria.

Parental involvement in school management refers to the meaningful and active participation of parents in shaping school policies, governance structures, and practices that directly influence pupils' learning and overall development. This participation may take different forms, including serving on school boards or committees, contributing to decision-making on curriculum and discipline policies, supporting school financing initiatives, and engaging in volunteer and fundraising activities (Mapp & Kuttner, 2022). Beyond policy-level engagement, parents also contribute by supporting the maintenance of school facilities, supervising homework, and monitoring their children's attendance and behaviour, all of which are associated with improved academic outcomes (Jeynes, 2023). According to Henderson and Mapp (2022), active parental engagement in school management strengthens collaboration between families and schools, enhances school climate, and promotes learners' motivation and achievement. Schools that foster such partnerships often experience higher learner performance and stronger community relationships. In view of these benefits, this study examined the impact of parental involvement in school management on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East, Nigeria, with particular focus on financing, maintenance of infrastructure, decision-making, maintenance of discipline, and monitoring of homework.

Involvement in financing appears to be one of the crucial dimensions of parents' participation in school management. Parents' involvement in school financing refers to the active contribution of financial resources, fundraising efforts and material support by parents to enhance school facilities and learning opportunities, thereby promoting improved educational outcomes (Epstein, 2018). Through these contributions, parents help provide essential resources, such as books, technology, and other learning materials that directly enrich pupils' educational experiences and outcomes (Jeynes, 2018). Hornby and Blackwell (2018) emphasize that schools with active parental financial support are better positioned to maintain and improve their facilities, which positively impacts pupil motivation and academic achievement. Furthermore, parental involvement in school financing strengthens the partnership between families and schools, fostering accountability and increasing pupil engagement and commitment to learning (Kim & Hill, 2015). In situations where government funding falls short, parental financial support becomes essential, bridging gaps that could otherwise hinder academic progress (Wilder, 2019). Parental involvement in school financing is deeply rooted in the understanding that education is a shared responsibility among stakeholders; government, school authorities, teachers, and the community. Recent studies show that when parents are financially engaged, schools' benefit from improved accountability, resource management and stronger stakeholder relationships (Ogunyemi & Olatunde, 2022). In situations where parental engagement is institutionalized, such as through active PTA frameworks, decision-making around expenditure becomes more transparent and responsive to community needs. Parents are not only financial contributors but also act as watchdogs who ensure that resources are used effectively. For instance, in Lagos and Cross River States, it has been reported that parents who were included in budget planning committees helped prevent misappropriation of school funds and advocated for more equitable spending (Aderibigbe, 2020). This participatory approach aligns with global best practices in school governance, where community ownership of educational processes enhances school effectiveness. These contributions not only provide essential resources but also demonstrate parents' commitment to supporting the school in maintaining and improving its infrastructure for the benefit of their children's education.

Parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure refers to the active participation of parents in supporting the repair, upkeep, and improvement of school facilities to promote a safe and effective learning environment (Teryima, 2022). Parents often play a direct role in supporting and sustaining school facilities, helping to create an environment conducive to learning by assisting with repairs, upgrades and upkeep (Abdullahi, 2020). For instance, in resource-limited schools, parents might organize community fundraising efforts to repair classrooms, improve sanitation facilities, or provide better seating and learning spaces, all of which are shown to positively affect learners' attendance and engagement (Epstein, 2018). Research suggests that well-maintained school environments contribute to higher levels of pupil motivation and academic performance, as learners feel safer and more valued in clean, functional, and welcoming schools (Gershenson, Hart, Lindsay, & Papageorge, 2017). In

communities where government maintenance budgets are inadequate, parental involvement becomes a crucial source of support, ensuring that pupils have access to safe, comfortable learning spaces that foster academic success (Smith, Johnson, & Nguyen, 2020). Based on the above submissions, one would say that when parents actively participate in maintaining school infrastructure, they not only enhance the learning environment but also foster a sense of ownership and accountability toward the school.

Maintaining school infrastructure is indeed an investment in the future of education and parents have a significant role to play in this process, especially in contexts where government funding is limited. Parents' involvement in school infrastructure maintenance has been acknowledged as a critical component of community participation in education. According to Agbatogun and Popoola (2021), schools that actively involve parents in maintenance activities experience improved infrastructural conditions and enhanced accountability in resource use. In many Nigerian public primary schools, especially in rural areas, parent-teacher associations (PTAs) often serve as the primary support system for infrastructure upkeep. They contribute funds, provide labour and oversee minor repair projects such as fixing leaking roofs, fencing school compounds and repairing damaged furniture. For instance, in Oju LGA of Benue State, parents in some schools collectively funded the renovation of dilapidated classrooms after government interventions failed to materialize (Okoh & Tor, 2024). This type of grassroots participation helps in fostering a sense of ownership and strengthens the link between families and the school system.

Despite the many ways in which parents can contribute to school management, through financing and maintaining infrastructure, these efforts appear to have limited tangible impact on pupils' academic performance, which continues to decline. Although research consistently emphasizes the positive impact of parental involvement on educational outcomes, evidence from practice indicates that these expected improvements are not always achieved. This discrepancy may stem from factors such as limited parental awareness of their critical role in supporting school management and fostering pupils' academic performance. In view of the above background, the researcher deems it essential to investigate the impact of parents' involvement in school management, particularly in the areas of school financing and maintenance of school infrastructure on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Pupils' academic performance is one of the most critical indicators of a functional, results-oriented school system that appears to be a major source of national concern today. In many schools, learners are struggling to achieve basic competencies in core subjects such as literacy, numeracy and science, and their performance on internal assessments and standardized examinations continues to fall (Audu, 2022). This decline reflects not only gaps in teaching quality and learning effectiveness but also inadequate learning support, which may have been caused by poor motivation and insufficient resources. Such persistent underperformance seems to threaten the overall quality of education and raises serious concerns about the readiness of future graduates to contribute meaningfully to national development, which depends on the knowledge, skills and competencies acquired at the foundational stages of education.

The researcher finds this situation deeply worrisome and is compelled to question which factors may be responsible for the persistent decline in academic performance, as evidenced by low scores in core subjects such as literacy, numeracy and science, high failure rates in internal and external examinations, poor class participation and a noticeable lack of mastery of foundational skills among pupils. Despite heavy government investments in the education sector aimed at improving infrastructure, the decline continues almost unabated. This raises a critical suspicion that the problem may lie in parents' lack of active involvement in their children's education. Education, being an expensive and shared responsibility, cannot thrive on government efforts alone. Parents are expected to complement government initiatives by enrolling their children, providing learning materials, and supporting their academic progress through moral and emotional guidance. Unfortunately, reports from teachers and administrators paint a gloomy picture; many parents appear to show little or no interest in the decision-making process at their children's schools, often missing opportunities to attend open days, PTAs, and SBMC meetings where they could engage with teachers and school management (Akpen, 2021). This lack of involvement seems to affect not only school operations but also their children's academic outcomes. Some parents visit the school only

when disciplinary actions are taken against their children, at times even confronting school staff, thereby disrupting the peace and even damaging school property. In response to these challenges, this study sought to investigate the impact of parental involvement in school management, in the areas of school financing and maintenance of infrastructure on pupil academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District of Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of parental involvement in school management on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. find out the impact of parents' involvement in school financing on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.
2. examine the impact of parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of parents' involvement in school financing on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria?
2. What impact does parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure have on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Parents' involvement in school financing has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.
2. Parents' involvement in maintenance of school infrastructure has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study, with a population of 5,561 teachers from 795 public primary schools in Benue North-East Senatorial District. Using a multistage sampling procedure, a sample of 371 teachers was selected from 37 public primary schools. Data were collected using the Parental Involvement and Pupils' Academic Performance Questionnaire (PIPAPQ), while mean scores and standard deviations were employed to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data collected for the study. A total of 371 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents, out of which 367 (99%) were properly completed and returned, while 4 (1%) were returned but not completed. The incomplete copies of the questionnaire were largely attributed to the busy schedules of some respondents, who intended to complete them but were unable to do so due to time constraints. The data were analyzed and interpreted based on the questions raised and the hypotheses formulated for the study.

Question One: *What is the impact of parents' involvement in school financing on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the Impact of Parents' Involvement in School Financing on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools

S/No	Items Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Parental financial support enables the school to pay for competent part-time teachers, improving pupils' understanding and examination results.	96	168	78	25	2.91	0.86	Agreed
2	Parents fund academic competitions and prizes, which motivate pupils to work harder and perform better.	108	162	80	17	2.98	0.84	Agreed
3	PTA contributions from parents are used to support the purchase of textbooks, leading to better class performance and study habits.	94	175	88	10	2.96	0.78	Agreed
4	Parents support the school in funding mock or preparatory examinations, improving pupils' examination preparedness and confidence.	105	172	71	19	2.99	0.83	Agreed
5	Parental funding ensures supply of chalk, markers, and other resources that support effective teaching and pupil comprehension.	92	190	70	15	2.98	0.78	Agreed
Cluster Mean						2.96		Agreed

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2026)

Table 1 shows that the mean ratings of items 1-5 are 2.91, 2.98, 2.96, 2.99 and 2.98 with the corresponding standard deviations of 0.86, 0.84, 0.78, 0.83 and 0.78, respectively. From Table 1, the respondents agreed that parental financial support enables the school to pay for competent part-time teachers which improving pupils' understanding and examination results, and that parents fund academic competitions and prizes, which motivate pupils to work harder and perform better. The respondents further agreed that PTA contributions from parents are used to support the purchase of textbooks, leading to better class performance and study habits. In addition, the respondents also opined that parent support the school in funding mock or preparatory examinations, improving pupils' examination preparedness and confidence. Moreover, the respondents agreed that parental funding ensures supply of chalk, markers and other resources that support effective teaching and pupil comprehension. The cluster mean of 2.96 was above the cut-off point of 2.50. This means that parents' involvement in school financing have impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Question Two: *What impact does parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure have on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Respondents on the Impact of Parents' Involvement in the Maintenance of School Infrastructure on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools

S/No	Items Description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Parents assist in renovating classrooms, providing pupils with a conducive environment for concentration and learning.	110	152	86	19	2.96	0.86	Agreed
7	Parents contribute to repairing broken desks and chairs, which helps pupils maintain proper posture and focus during classwork.	95	183	75	14	2.98	0.79	Disagreed
8	Parents support the maintenance of clean toilets, reducing absenteeism and supporting continuous academic engagement.	98	170	72	27	2.92	0.87	Agreed
9	Parents help maintain sports facilities, improving pupils' physical well-being and academic readiness.	108	184	63	12	3.06	0.77	Agreed
10	Replacing worn-out blackboards through parents' support helps improve lesson clarity and pupils' understanding.	100	168	74	25	2.93	0.86	Agreed
Cluster Mean						2.97		Agreed

Source: Researcher's Field Survey (2026)

Table 2 shows that the mean ratings of items 6-10 are 2.96, 2.98, 2.92, 2.96 and 2.93 with the corresponding standard deviations of 0.86, 0.79, 0.87, 0.77 and 0.86, respectively. Item-by-item analysis showed that respondents agreed that parents assist in renovating classrooms, providing pupils with a conducive environment for concentration and learning. They also indicated that parents contribute to repairing broken desks and chairs, which helps pupils maintain proper posture and focus during classwork. They also agree that parents support the maintenance of clean toilets, reducing absenteeism and supporting continuous academic engagement and that parents help maintain sports facilities, improving pupils' physical well-being and academic readiness. In addition, the respondents agreed that replacing worn-out blackboards through parents' support helps improve lesson clarity and pupils' understanding. The cluster mean of 2.97 was above the cut-off point of 2.50. This means that parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure have impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One: Parents' involvement in school financing has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-square test of the Impact of Parents' Involvement in School Financing on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df	Level of Sig.	χ^2 -Cal.	P-value	Decision
SA	99	91.8	3	0.05	134.177 ^a	.000	Significant
A	173	91.8					
D	77	91.8					
SD	18	91.8					
Total	367						

$P=.000 < 0.05$; $df=3$; and χ^2 -calculated = 134.177.

Table 3 shows that $P < .05$ with 3 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that parents' involvement in school financing has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, was rejected. This result clearly showed that parents' involvement in school financing has significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Parents' involvement in maintenance of school infrastructure has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square test of the Impact of Parents' Involvement in Maintenance of School Infrastructure on Pupils' Academic Performance in Public Primary Schools

Responses	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df	Level of Sig.	χ^2 -Cal.	P-value	Decision
SA	102	91.8	3	0.05	129.142 ^a	.000	Significant
A	171	91.8					
D	74	91.8					
SD	20	91.8					
Total	367						

$P=.000 < 0.05$; $df=3$; and χ^2 -calculated = 129.142.

Table 4 shows that $P < .05$ with 3 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that parents' involvement in maintenance of school infrastructure has no significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria, was rejected. This result implies that parents' involvement in maintenance of school infrastructure has significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the impact of parental involvement in school management on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. The findings are discussed in relation to the study's variables.

The first finding revealed that parents' involvement in school financing has a significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. This is justified by the fact that when parents actively contribute financially to school activities, institutions are better positioned to provide essential learning resources, improve infrastructure, and create supportive teaching and learning conditions that enhance pupils' academic outcomes. The finding aligns with Moyo (2020), who reported a moderate positive correlation between the level of parental financial involvement and pupils' performance in literacy and numeracy. The study further indicated that schools with active Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs), which contribute to instructional materials, infrastructural development, and teacher incentives, recorded significantly higher academic achievement. Similarly, Ncube and Kwenha (2019) found that parental involvement in financing learning aids and supporting school projects significantly contributed to improved academic success among pupils. This means that when parents participate in financial decision-making processes in schools, accountability and transparency are strengthened, leading to more effective utilization of resources and improved learning outcomes. In the same vein, Banda (2021) reported that schools where parents consistently supported the provision of textbooks, school meals and infrastructural maintenance experienced better performance in national assessments. The present finding is consistent with these studies, as it demonstrates that parental financial involvement plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of the learning environment, increasing pupils' engagement and improving overall academic performance. Conversely, a lack of financial collaboration between parents and schools often results in inadequate learning facilities, poor school environments, and reduced pupil motivation, which negatively affect academic achievement. The current study, therefore, contends that strengthening parental financial participation through structured platforms such as PTAs is not merely supportive but essential for improving pupils' academic performance and ensuring sustainable educational development in public primary schools.

The second finding revealed that parents' involvement in the maintenance of school infrastructure has significant impact on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. This is justified by the fact that when parents actively participate in maintaining school facilities, such as classrooms, sanitation systems and school surroundings, they help create a safe, clean and conducive learning environment that supports effective teaching and learning. Such environments enhance pupils' concentration, attendance and overall engagement in academic activities, thereby improving their academic performance. The finding aligns with Wambua (2021), who found that pupils in schools where parents were actively involved in infrastructure maintenance performed significantly better in literacy and numeracy assessments. Similarly, Dlamini and Nkosi (2020) reported that consistent parental involvement in school maintenance activities, including classroom repairs, sanitation and school fencing, had a positive impact on student attendance and test scores. In the same vein, Tetteh (2022) observed that schools with strong parent-led maintenance initiatives experienced fewer disruptions to academic activities, improved pupil morale and higher average academic performance. Tetteh further acknowledged that proactive parental participation in infrastructure upkeep is essential for sustaining a conducive learning environment. The present finding is consistent with these studies, as it demonstrates that parents' involvement in maintaining school infrastructure contributes significantly to improved learning conditions, increased pupil engagement, and enhanced academic performance. The current study, therefore, contends that encouraging and strengthening parental participation in school infrastructure maintenance is essential for promoting effective learning and improving pupils' academic performance in public primary schools.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that parents' involvement in school financing and maintenance of school infrastructure plays a critical role in shaping pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Benue North East Senatorial District, Nigeria. These dimensions of involvement are not merely supportive but fundamental to the effective functioning of schools and the overall learning outcomes of pupils. However, the findings present a worrisome reality: where parental involvement in these key areas is weak, inconsistent or absent, the consequences for pupils' academic performance can be severe. Poor school funding, deteriorating infrastructure collectively create an unfavourable learning environment. If these issues are not urgently addressed, they may lead to a sustained decline in academic standards, increased cases of poor learning outcomes and a generation of pupils inadequately prepared for higher educational pursuits and societal responsibilities.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and education policymakers should develop and strengthen policies that encourage active parental participation in school financing through structured mechanisms such as Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) and community-based funding initiatives. School administrators should ensure transparency and accountability in the utilization of such funds to encourage parents to contribute regularly and responsibly to support school needs.
2. School administrators and local education authorities should actively involve parents in the maintenance and improvement of school infrastructure through collaborative programmes such as community development projects and school maintenance committees.

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